

Communities of Practice Governance Framework

D 6.2

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
Ch	Chapter
CoP	Communities of Practice
CRN	Co-creation and Replication Node
D.	Deliverable
FAO	Food and agriculture organization
FLW	Food loss and waste
FLWPR	Food loss and waste prevention and reduction
FSC	Food Supply Chain
JRC	European Commission Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key performance indicator
SRAF	Sustainability Risk Assessment Framework
T.	Task
UC	Use Cases
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Project Overview

If food loss and waste (FLW) were a country, it would be the third leading cause of greenhouse gas emissions. FLW also burdens waste management systems and exacerbates food insecurity, contributing significantly to the three global crises of climate change, nature and biodiversity loss, and pollution and waste.

PRECIOUS, a transdisciplinary alliance of 18 entities from 11 EU countries, believes that reliable data on the environmental impacts of FLW is crucial for accelerating EU progress towards climate targets and reducing environmental impacts (including biodiversity) across the food supply chain. The project's collective understanding is that the challenge goes beyond measuring the amount of food saved or CO₂ emissions. When food is wasted, valuable and limited resources, such as water, land, and energy are also lost. Meanwhile 8.9% of the worldwide population is suffering from hunger according to FAO, therefore, depleting the planet's natural resources. It is critical to broaden our understanding of the issue to transform the food system and raise public awareness that motivates change.

PRECIOUS aims to contribute to transforming food systems by addressing existing data gaps and developing a unified and openly accessible evaluation framework to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of strategies to reduce FLW, considering potential rebound effects.

The project will engage stakeholders from 2 Use Cases (Spain and Greece) and 3 Co-creation and Replication Nodes (Poland, Lithuania, Hungary) to address systemic causes across geographical boundaries. The project aims to induce a fundamental change in attitudes and behaviours towards food consumption and disposal through collaborative efforts and innovative methods, fostering a more just and sustainable EU food system.

1.2. Deliverable Summary

A Community of Practice (CoP) is a stakeholder engagement format to facilitate peer learning, mutual support, and collaboration. The PRECIOUS project establishes two CoPs in Greece and Spain, respectively, with the aim of co-creating PRECIOUS food loss and waste prevention and reduction actions, as well as their assessment. The present document outlines a Governance Framework for these CoPs, providing details on the Strategy and Approach, including monitoring and evaluation, and suggests a Local Implementation Plan. Additionally, it offers a Manual with concrete instructions, templates, and tools setting up and implementing the CoPs. It is intended to support in particular the PRECIOUS project partners responsible for facilitating the CoPs. The framework supports their efforts in implementing and facilitating CoPs to ensure long-term engagement, promote knowledge exchange, and translate project insights into actionable outcomes.

This deliverable builds upon the Stakeholder Mapping D6.1. and aims to foster close practical synergies between WP6 and WP3, as well as tasks 1.4, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, and 6.3.

Against this background, the document aims to guide CoP hosts, as well as the PRECIOUS consortium, in organizing of CoPs as an effective stakeholder engagement tool.

2. Introduction

The PRECIOUS project aims to contribute to transforming food systems by addressing existing data gaps and developing a unified and openly accessible evaluation framework to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of strategies to reduce FLW, considering potential rebound effects. Central to this mission is the engagement of stakeholders through Communities of Practice (CoPs) – collaborative spaces designed to co-create solutions, foster innovation, and drive the uptake of food loss and waste prevention and reduction (FLWPR) actions across the food system of Western Macedonia (Greece) and northwestern Spain. The CoPs complement the Use Cases (UCs), which focus on the food supply chain stages of specific businesses, by expanding stakeholder engagement to a wider scope and contributing to regional and context-specific adaptation of FLWPR actions.

2.1. Objective

This **CoP Governance Framework** serves as a practical guide for PRECIOUS project partners responsible for facilitating these CoPs. The framework supports their efforts in implementing and facilitating CoPs to ensure long-term engagement, promote knowledge exchange, and translate project insights into actionable outcomes.

This document is deliberately designed to provide practical guidance for CoP hosts and project partners by outlining the engagement process and discussion priorities, including monitoring and evaluation.

- At the beginning of the CoP creation (starting M10), **CoP hosts** should read the full document to get a general understanding of the approach and underlying strategy.
- During the CoP implementation (M12-M48), to which more details are provided in section 4.3, **CoP hosts and WP, as well as task leaders**, are invited to register to specific sections based on the concrete activities planned and undertaken. The content of this CoP Governance Framework is further shaped in a way to allow **Task 6.3 (T6.3) partners** to gain insights for the Co-creation and Replication Nodes (CRNs).

2.2. Structure

The **CoP Governance Framework** is structured into three main sections:

- The first section, **→ Strategy and Approach** (Chapter 3), introduces – in alignment with European best practices – the conceptual foundation of the CoPs, with a focus on co-creation and an inclusive engagement process.
- The second section **→ Local Implementation Plan** (Chapter 4) provides an introduction to the two CoP profiles, an overview table jointly mapping CoP and PRECIOUS needs for stakeholder engagement and thereby hinting towards the discussion priorities. A timeline for the engagement process is suggested.
- The Annex, as the third section, serves as **→ Manual** (Annex), offering concrete instructions for planning and running CoP sessions, important monitoring and evaluation, as well as other relevant activities. The instructions are complemented by templates and tools.

Cross-references to relevant sections within this document – and to the Stakeholder Mapping (D.6.1.) – are visually highlighted by an arrow **→** and with **white text on a turquoise background**.

2.3. Methodology

The PRECIOUS CoP Governance Framework takes the recent European Commission **Joint Research Centre publication** “The Communities of Practice Playbook. A playbook to collectively run and develop communities of practice”¹ as general guidance.

It is also grounded in extensive own experience by the CSCP thanks to its CoP steering in **earlier EU projects**, including [PathoCERT](#) and [CCRI CoP](#), such as related formats as in [iCOSHELLs](#).

Furthermore, the framework is informed by an **interactive internal alignment process** amongst project partners. This included multiple bilateral meetings between task leads, as well as interactive sessions with all partners engaged in WP6 to identify their needs and wants for stakeholder engagement, as well as to adjust the framework to harness synergies between tasks. Additionally, the CoP Governance Framework builds on the [→Stakeholder Mapping and Initial Engagement Plan](#) (D.6.1), which addresses first ideas for stakeholder engagement, engagement entry points, and discussion priorities.

2.4. Definitions

A **Community of Practice (CoP)** consists a group of stakeholders with a shared interest for a topic or concern. coming together to engage in mutual learning, knowledge sharing, and improving their skills through ongoing interaction. It is a stakeholder engagement format aiming to enhance collaboration and mutual support for shared interests or concerns. By facilitating collaboration between stakeholders, CoPs can contribute to solving complex problems, characterised by uncertainties or structural barriers.

CoPs are a strong method for long-term and systemic change. Through the continuous dialogue and collaboration between stakeholders, they extend the life of projects beyond their temporal scope, ensuring that the impact and networks created are long-lasting. Members of the CoPs also learn valuable skills and gain insights through the knowledge sharing practices, empowering them to implement and lead solutions and initiatives.

Within PRECIOUS, the Use Cases (UCs) focus on individual food supply chains, while the CoPs build on UCs’ insights to foster cross-stage collaboration, knowledge exchange, and long-term regional change beyond the UCs’ scope. Further details on the alignment between the UCs and the CoPs are outlined in [→Chapter 4.4.](#)

The **CoP host** is the local facilitator and coordinator who steers the CoP process and convenes relevant stakeholders. The host therefore plays a crucial role in connecting the community and its stakeholders with the broader context and system. In the case of PRECIOUS, the host for the Spanish CoP is ASINCAR, and the Greek CoP is hosted by CluBE. Within PRECIOUS, at least 5 CoP sessions will be organised as central opportunities for members to come together and exchange. Between the sessions, the CoP hosts will facilitate communication and interaction with the CoP members.

CoP membership is an open concept. Any interested stakeholder across supply chain stages or relevant to the issue at stake, typically practitioners but also such as cross-stage actors like policy makers, can be a **member of the CoP**. The community evolves further as more members join and bring in their knowledge, needs and interests. This can occur naturally by stakeholders discovering the CoP and requesting to join. Membership can and should also actively be steered by the CoP host and members, who may want to extend invitations to key stakeholders that might not have been part of the process yet. The focus in PRECIOUS is on regional and

¹ JRC (2021): The Communities of Practice Playbook. A playbook to collectively run and develop communities. <https://doi.org/10.2760/42416>

national actors in the two CoP communities, united by a common interest or influence to reduce food loss and waste.

The core group is a round of members, including the CoP host and CoP members, who actively convene between meetings and exchange on how to steer the community towards its objectives. The CoP host identifies members of the core group based on their characteristics. Members of the core group should be central actors, influencers, or decision makers in the area of the CoP.

→Chapter 3, strategy and approach provides more details on the core elements of successfully facilitating a CoP.

3. Strategy and approach

A CoP is a stakeholder engagement format to facilitate peer learning, mutual support, and collaboration. Practitioners share and steward a domain of knowledge with a collective intention. According to the Joint Research Centre (JRC 2021) there exist eight community success facets. They shall also guide this PRECIOUS CoP governance framework:

1. **Vision**
2. **Governance**
3. **Leadership**
4. **Convening**
5. **Collaboration and cooperation**
6. **Community management**
7. **User experience**
8. **Monitoring & Evaluation**

This chapter translates these success facets into core principles for PRECIOUS by taking both, the lens of the participating stakeholders, as well as the lens of the project's objectives to ensure impactful, sustainable, and stakeholder-driven PRECIOUS CoPs. It also formulates projects to do's per success facet.

3.1. Vision

Why does PRECIOUS create CoPs, what are the objectives and aims it aspires to achieve?

The CoPs within PRECIOUS shall serve as a participatory and co-creative platform contributing towards long-term engagement for the overarching objectives of PRECIOUS. Overall, the CoPs are an essential instrument of the project to enhance the identification and foster the uptake of stakeholder-driven food loss and waste prevention and reduction (FLWPR) actions and the aspect of rebound effects.

PRECIOUS To Do:

- **Setting a common goal** during one of the first CoP sessions helps to increase the common identity and interest. This could for instance be the goal to tailor policy recommendations to the local context, or to actively work towards implementing a set of solutions. Each CoP assess the most appropriate mechanisms to ensure stakeholder engagement with this goal (e.g. with a [→Declaration of Participation](#) (Annex 2) or alike).
- As the **stakeholder's interests and needs actively shape the scope, objectives, and trajectory** of each CoP, the CoP Host will take the [→CoP Profiles](#) (Ch. 4.1) as well as the [→CoP Engagement Decision and Entry Points](#) (Annex 1) as a **starting point for agenda planning and discussion**. This also contributes to the development of local ownership and collective impact for long-term collaboration.
- **Close exchanges amongst project partners** are key to enable the transfer of outputs of other project tasks into context-specific, co-developed solutions. Thereby, the CoPs can play a critical role in adapting the insights to the needs of diverse stakeholders and ultimately foster the successful uptake of FLWPR actions. The [→Mapping table](#) (Ch. 4.2) of thematic needs and regional situation shall help foster local ownership and facilitate lasting change beyond the project's duration, as outlined in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Synergies of good stakeholder engagement and good alignment of project tasks leading to sustained local and regional networks and FLWPR impact.

3.2. Governance

How do the partners work together, and with whom? And, how do they make decisions?

The objective will be to create with the CoPs an environment where people feel safe and encouraged to share their practice-related successes and failures and give open feedback to PRECIOUS draft work in order to bring the CoP Vision to life. ASINCAR and CLuBE will act as CoP hosts and facilitators for the PRECIOUS CoPs in Spain and Greece respectively. Influential, impacted and interested stakeholders will be invited to co-create the CoP, fostering co-ownership. The stakeholder mapping as well as this CoP governance framework prepared by the CSCP serve as supporting documents to steer the co-creation and co-ownership towards success. The CSCP as WP6 lead will furthermore guide and support the CoP hosts whenever necessary in the set-up and implementation of the CoP. PRECIOUS project partners will provide the necessary content, such as insights from related project tasks, to foster meaningful exchanges.

PRECIOUS To Do:

- While CoP Hosts will pro-actively steer the engagement, they will give room to co-create decision making and working practices. As underlined by JRC (2021), it is useful to formalize and explicitly describe the community operational model (e.g. Terms of references or Code of Conduct see [→Declaration of Participation](#) (Annex 2)) to all involved parties. This could be elaborated together, for example by using the [→Affinity Map](#) method suggested in the [→Interactive Methods Descriptions](#) (Annex 2).
- The CoP includes participants from diverse sectors: producers, processors, retailers, consumers, policymakers, civil society, academia, and startups. CoP Hosts will aim for a **valuable stakeholder composition** along all food supply chain stages, inspired by the PRECIOUS [→Stakeholder Mapping](#) (D6.1.). This mapping enabled an organized overview of which stakeholders are of most influential, who will be impacted and who is / will get involved, based on an initial understanding

of what they do and what they need. A high diversity is desirable, but can also mean a diversity of expectations and needs. CoP Hosts will have to take this into consideration.

- **Membership** is voluntary and open to any stakeholder committed to the objectives of the CoP. Members are encouraged to participate actively, share experiences, and support collective goals. The specific engagement can be defined with a [→Declaration of Participation](#) (Annex 2). The CoP grows as new members join, contributing their expertise, needs, and interests. This can happen organically when stakeholders find the CoP and ask to participate. Additionally, the host and members should actively invite important stakeholders who have not yet been involved.
- **To ensure transparency** of the CoP processes, **short summaries of the discussions** will be shared with the CoP participants. Unless otherwise discussed and decided by the CoP itself, this will happen at least by mail – other communication channels (e.g. publication on a website or online forum) to be decided.

3.3. Leadership

How will the partners ensure strong leadership participation?

As described by JRC (2021), a core group of community members taking the lead and steering the community is a key success element. Their support for the CoP Hosts and visible acknowledgment of the CoP impact are needed. The community appreciates and values their input.

PRECIOUS To Do:

- To identify the leaders that can support the CoPs, **CoP Hosts will consider the potential influence of the involved stakeholders**. Initial insights can be gained from the Impact, Interest and Cross-stage dependence rating in the [→Stakeholder Mapping](#) (D6.1.).
- **Relevant leadership roles** include the role of active and driving participant, as well as promoter and creator of visibility. PRECIOUS will discuss internally how to best inspire active participation of senior and middle managers in these roles.

3.4. Convening

What kind of convening opportunities work for the CoP?

The participating stakeholders invest their precious time to become members of the CoP. Thus, not only should all agenda items in PRECIOUS CoP activities provide value for them – as well as to serve the purposes and objectives of the project –, the outreach and invitation to the chosen stakeholders has to be well deliberated.

PRECIOUS To Do's:

- Each CoP will organize **five or more CoP meetings** as a means for regular interaction. While it is recommended to host the first and last session in person, to secure the commitment, the CoP hosts may choose to host online or hybrid sessions if this allows a better inclusion of diverse stakeholders. Depending on the objectives of the meeting and the wishes of the participants, the other meetings can either take place physically or online – the latter may support discussions of urgent issues and also the involvement of more participants. The [→Action Timeline](#) (Chapter 4.3) provides guidance on the timing of the meetings. The frequency and objectives of meetings can however always be adapted and co-developed with the CoP members.
- For each CoP activity – particularly meetings – **CoP hosts supported by CSCP will use the [→Planning and Running a CoP Session](#)** (Annex 2) – particularly sections [→WHEN](#) and [→WHO](#) – to define discuss and decide how to create the space for the planned engagement. This includes logistics, meeting mode (physical or online), frequency and invitation strategy.

- The analysis of the **composition of stakeholder groups, their position within the food supply chain, and their interests and challenges** within the [→Stakeholder Mapping](#) (D6.1.) provides an important basis for CoP hosts to define and refine their invitation strategy and the engagement approaches to mitigate risks and enhance effectiveness in achieving both the project’s objectives and stakeholder needs. For the convenience of the CoP Hosts, the extracts can be found in the Annex in [→COP Engagement Decision and Entry Points](#) (Annex 1).

3.5. Collaboration and Cooperation

How does PRECIOUS co-create and coordinate different cooperation and collaboration processes to deliver concrete community knowledge?

A unique feature of the CoP as a stakeholder engagement format is that all members are invested into the topics and can be considered experts. Thus, they can mutually exchange ideas and learn about challenges and solutions that fit their specific context. As a result, CoPs can foster long-lasting collaboration that caters to the exact needs and context of the members to facilitate effective change.

PRECIOUS To Do:

- **Co-develop local solutions from broader project insights.** The CoPs want to learn from and actively involve local, regional and national stakeholders to make solutions more tangible and facilitate the uptake of the solutions. For each CoP activity – particularly meetings – **CoP hosts supported by CSCP will use the [→Planning and Running a CoP meeting](#)** (Annex 2) – particularly sections [→WHY, HOW](#) and [Let’s ENGAGE](#) – to define discuss and decide how to do the work once people are convened. This includes focusing on the outputs, solving problems and generating value.
- **Integrate project tasks to add value for members:** In PRECIOUS this will be achieved by creating meaningful engagement of other tasks’ stakeholder input needs, instead of simply “ticking a box”. To this end, the [→Local Implementation Plan](#) (Ch. 4) makes suggestions on how to integrate the CoPs with other project tasks, and how this can add value for the members.
- **Co-develop of innovative business cases.** Enhance the potential for FLWPR-related start-ups and business opportunities to emerge and scale within the regions, by bringing together key stakeholders and contributing to more supportive policy landscapes.
- **Co-create and highlight outputs** (e.g. policy briefs, pilots, toolkits, good practices) by tailoring other project tasks’ outputs to the specific needs and interests of the CoP members, and by co-developing own outputs, which address their needs. Highlighting and disseminating them in the networks of the CoP members can facilitate further FLWPR and the development of new opportunities.

3.6. Community Management

How do partners facilitate dynamic and synchronous community interactions?

A CoP is not rigid. It is a co-creative effort and should constantly adapt to the goals, interests, and needs of the participating stakeholders. The members actively shape the CoPs direction. Hence, the CoP should not stay a stale and theoretical endeavour.

PRECIOUS To Do:

- While the [→Local Implementation Plan](#) (Ch. 4) provides guidance on integrating project tasks, it is not a rigid set of steps. Instead, consider the **Local Implementation Plan** as the starting point, while remaining open to explore the interest of your members.

- For each CoP activity – particularly meetings – **CoP hosts supported by CSCP will brainstorm on the most suitable format**, thereby being inspired by the [→Interactive Methods Descriptions](#) (Annex 2).
- **Keep it active.** The CoPs will actively test members' ideas and be open to different formats and topics.
- The CoP members will decide collaboratively if they would like to have and use a mailing list, a shared cloud storage, an own LinkedIn group, or any other **tools that support their collaboration**.

3.7. User Experience

How do PRECIOUS CoPs ensure a member-centric community experience while performing project tasks set and supporting members' needs?

PRECIOUS will focus on the members interest and identity of the members that have initially been identified by the CoP Hosts (see [→Stakeholder Mapping D6.1.](#); for further information see also [→COP Engagement Decision and Entry Points](#) (Annex 1)). The intention is that the interests of the members should guide the focus of the CoP, while CoP hosts synergistically integrate the needs and wishes of the PRECIOUS work packages and tasks. The meetings should actively address the key interests of the participating stakeholders and focus on identified challenges to identify solutions.

PRECIOUS To Do's:

- For both CoPs this means **addressing the challenges identified** and briefly presented in the [→CoP Profiles](#) (Ch. 4.1), such as the difficulty of engaging the consumer stage, and adapting to evolving policy landscapes. It also implies actively responding to the topic demanded by topics from the members.
- For each CoP activity – particularly meetings – **CoP hosts will gather participant feedback**, and are invited to use the templates provided on [→Participant Survey](#) and [→Feedback Survey](#) (both Annex 3).

3.8. Monitoring & Evaluation

How will PRECIOUS understand and measure the CoP vitality? What will it learn from it?

The CoPs are the instruments of the PRECIOUS project to contribute in targeting the needs of the relevant (end-) users of the project results, to build upon existing practices and to unite stakeholders in knowledge exchange and dialogue. PRECIOUS WP 6 thereby aims to ensure that the project outputs are relevant to the situation of diverse stakeholders and will eventually put into practice. Continuous monitoring and evaluation serve the purpose of assessing whether the project is on track to achieve this overarching goal.

PRECIOUS To Do's:

- CoP Hosts, supported by CSCP, will undertake monitoring to keep track of essential KPIs and objectives. CoP Hosts will find guidance in the [→Monitoring & Evaluation Description](#) (Annex 3).
- Use evaluation (e.g. gathered via the [→Participant Survey](#) and [→Feedback Survey](#) templates (Annex 3)) as feedback to tailor the next individual CoP meetings / activities to the needs and wants of the stakeholders and project tasks.

- The [→Meeting Report](#) (Annex 3) enables to capture immediate reflection on what worked and what did not. These will be filled in by the CoP host post-meeting and implications for the CoP's strategy will collaboratively be discussed with the CSCP.
- CSCP as WP6 lead will build upon the CoP monitoring and evaluation as essential elements of the planned *Impact Workshop* (M19), as well as for D6.3, the *Impact assessment and updated stakeholder engagement plan* (M48). These will serve as important periodic reflections.

4. Local Implementation Plan

The Local Implementation Plan provides guidance for the CoP hosts on how to design the CoPs’ trajectories. It consists of three segments.

- It first provides short profiles of the two CoPs with their local challenges, their preliminary scope and goals, and regional opportunities.
- Afterwards, related project tasks’ needs for stakeholder engagement and how these tasks can provide value to the participating stakeholders are shortly described in a table, by matching them with the regional situation.
- Finally, a timeline is presented, listing all relevant steps for both CoP locations, including when to plan, run, and report on CoP meetings, and when to align with other project tasks.

You can use this local implementation plan as a starting point for how to integrate your project tasks, but make sure you stay open to the interests of your participants. → [Community Management](#) (Ch. 3.6.).

4.1. The PRECIOUS CoP Profiles

Bilateral alignment calls and interactive sessions in the WP6 meetings, and the identification of engagement entry and discussion points in D6.1 (see also → [COP Engagement Decision and Entry Points](#) (Annex 1) contributed to profiling both CoPs. The profiles outline FLWPR-related challenges and potential discussion priorities, the preliminary scope of the CoPs, which will be further shaped by CoP participants, and potential synergies that can be built on. All of these items inform the planning of the CoPs’ trajectories (→ [Vision](#)) (Ch. 3.1.).

For the CoP hosts, these profiles serve as compact summaries to develop the preliminary scope of the CoPs, before agreeing on the vision and objectives with the CoP members. For project partners, particularly task leads under WP5, the profiles serve as an anchor to integrate project tasks with the CoPs from the beginning.

Table 1. CoP Profiles

Greek CoP
hosted by CluBE

Challenges

- Consumer behaviour, food waste in the retail stage, packaging and storage are some of the diverse challenges across the food supply chain.
- Supply chain inefficiencies caused by overall insufficient data and monitoring, infrastructure, governance and policy support.
- Difficulty to ensure long-term commitment from stakeholders and tailoring policy recommendations to local conditions.
- Potential regional and national stakeholder retention.

Spanish CoP
hosted by ASINCAR

Challenges

- Difficulty to integrate the consumer stage, where most food waste occurs and expertise is limited.
- Insufficient data on consumer behaviour and waste patterns.
- Different levels of expertise and demand for legal and policy insights (e.g. emerging Spanish FLW law) by different stakeholders.
- Difficulty securing long-term commitment with different motivators across producers, retailers, civil society and startups.
- Need to align cross-cutting objectives (sustainability, bioeconomy, social impact) without diluting focus on core use cases.

- Integration of consumers.

Preliminary Scope & Goals

- Focusing on the regional level in Western Macedonia with selected stakeholders from national and local level.
- Fostering knowledge exchange to address cross-sectoral challenges, especially in terms of policy support and infrastructure.
- Facilitating the uptake of best practices and the development of new FLWPR-focused initiatives and business ideas through effective cross-stage collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Synergies & Opportunities

- Explore synergies with current regional bioeconomy-related networks on policy, innovation and economic development.

Preliminary Scope & Goals

- Regional focus on northwestern Spanish regions of Asturias, Galicia, and Castilly y León, engaging the entire FSC, including consumer-stage experts and surveys.
- Foster knowledge exchange to uncover common challenges and support collaborative solutions.
- Foster innovation pathways, i.e. by catalysing startups or initiatives for upcycled livestock residues, collagen, bio-residues and other FLWPR actions.

Synergies & Opportunities

- Collaboration with the SPRINT project for consumer-waste data via their consumer-facing app.
- Leverage in-house expertise and relations with experts to brief stakeholders on policy developments.
- Leverage existing networks and collaborate with related projects.

4.2. Mapping thematic and regional needs and opportunities

This section provides CoP Hosts with an overview of the stakeholder input needs and opportunities to share valuable insights with CoP stakeholders, as identified by the PRECIOUS work packages and tasks. These reflect the initial planning outlined in the Grant Agreement and have since been refined and validated by the CSCP through collaborative discussions with all relevant work packages.

The following table provides an overview designed to help CoP Hosts identify where further exchange and in-depth discussions with project partners could generate added value for both participants and the project as a whole. This approach supports local ownership and encourages lasting impact beyond the project’s lifetime (→ [Vision Ch. 3.1](#)). The list is structured according to the approximate timelines of each task and includes potential keywords to help cluster and connect related topics. It also offers initial suggestions on which topics may be particularly relevant for each CoP (S = Spain, G = Greece), while leaving room for further discussion on the most suitable timing and context for addressing additional needs and opportunities.

A more detailed description of the respective tasks can be found in the Annex → [Project Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input](#) (Chapter 4.4). For each mentioned project task, the subsequent sections provide an overview of the task’s objectives, its needs (e.g. qualitative or quantitative data, verification or feedback), and the value that it provides to the CoP participants. The latter includes an outlook on how integrating a certain task can serve the participating stakeholders in their own mission and trajectory towards FLWPR.

Table 2. Mapping thematic and regional needs and opportunities

Task	Timeline	Needs for Stakeholder Input	Added Value for Stakeholders	Consumer	Policy	Technology	Data	Business	Multistakeholder	Local context	Education / awareness	Food chain
T1.4.	M4-M32		Supports identification of effective FLWPR actions, including spillover effect considerations, by investigating consumer responses and behavioral feedback loops.	S								
T1.4.	M4-M32	Collaboration with the entire CoP is not necessary.	Task 1.4 can provide context-specific insights into acceptance of upcycled food products at the consumer stage, a relevant challenge for both CoPs and CRNs.	S						S		
T1.4.	M4-M32	Acquiring local consumer insights in UC locations and Germany to provide context-specific understandings of consumer behaviors, perceptions, and barriers via quasi-experiments and interviews with a subset of the CoP stakeholders.	The insights will help with addressing consumer barriers regarding upcycled food products, avoiding social rebound effects, and improving consumer-facing communication.	S					S	S	S	
T1.4.	M4-M32		It can contribute to the goal of creating FLWPR-related start-ups, thanks to stakeholders' actions in the CoP regions.						S & G			
5.3.	M6-M48	Detect policy gaps and regulatory barriers that hinder FLW reduction efforts.	Tools to monitor and raise awareness of FLW in households.	S & G	S & G	S & G					S & G	
5.3.	M6-M48	Understand consumer behaviors that contribute to food loss and waste (FLW).	Strengthened consumer education to foster more sustainable consumption habits.	S							S	
5.3.	M6-M48	Identify the most significant points of loss in the local food supply chain (FSC).	Insights into consumer behavior and socioeconomic factors influencing FLW.	S					S	S		S
5.3.	M6-M48		Policy support and stronger enforcement of FLW-related action plans to ensure long-term impact.		S & G							
5.3.	M6-M48	Develop viable and scalable business models that support FLW prevention and reduction.	Identification and closure of infrastructure gaps in FLW management and valorization.					G				
5.3.	M6-M48	Provide reliable and relevant data to inform strategy development and decision-making.	Investments in local processing infrastructure to support food recovery and reuse.				G			G		
5.3.	M6-M48	Evaluate the environmental and social impacts of FLW across the FSC.	Improved access to EU and national funding opportunities for FLW initiatives.						S & G			S & G
5.3.	M6-M48		Financial support for upcycling and revaluation of by-products.									S & G

Task	Timeline	Needs for Stakeholder Input	Added Value for Stakeholders	Consumer	Policy	Technology	Data	Business	Multistakeholder	Local context	Education / awareness	Food chain
5.3.	M6-M48	Review existing food waste laws and evaluate their effectiveness and enforcement.	Implementation of FLWPR actions tailored to stakeholder contexts.						T B C			
5.3.	M6-M48	Identify opportunities to revalue or upcycle by-products (e.g., turning surplus into new products).	Enhanced ability to strategically plan interventions and prioritize actions based on data.				T B C					
5.3.	M6-M48	Explore strategies for preserving food and extending shelf life.	In-depth analysis of regional FLW data to identify local trends and hotspots.				T B C			T B C		
5.3.	M6-M48	Assess the limitations stakeholders face (financial, operational, regulatory, etc.) and their level of commitment to FLW reduction.	Access to structured data and prioritization tools to support evidence-based decision-making.			T B C	T B C		T B C			
5.1., 5.2.	M6-M24 M24- M46	Aim to have stakeholder input for the three target audiences: consumer, producers and supply chain actors, policy makers.		S & G	S & G				S & G			S & G
5.1., 5.2.	M6-M24 M24- M46	Qualitative and quantitative input for the identification, weighting, and design of model parameters.	Identification of sustainability risks						S & G	S & G		S & G
WP3	M9-M40	Understanding needs of stakeholders in relation to consumer behaviour change towards FLWPR beyond the use cases.	Learn from best practices and experiences developed in the Use Cases.	S					S			
5.1., 5.2.	M6-M24 M24- M46	Testing the model by performing an LCA.						S & G		S & G		
5.1., 5.2.	M6-M24 M24- M46	Identification of needs and the potential applications for the risk assessment framework by the stakeholders.	Design of a risk assessment framework tailored to stakeholders' needs and objectives.						T B C			
5.1., 5.2.	M6-M24 M24- M46	Operationalisation and validation of the model by a diverse set of stakeholders.	Development of a set framework to develop consistent strategies for FLWPR.						T B C			
WP3	M20- M24	Collaborate with stakeholders that can create positive impact for consumer behaviour, including European sister projects	Scale up practices to decrease the overall FLW in the FSCs.	S					S			
WP3	M26- M40	Develop solutions on FLWPR challenges through workshops and co-creation							S & G	S & G		S & G
5.5.	M24- M48	Validation of the policy recommendations via surveys, questionnaires, or workshops.			S & G							
5.5.	M24- M48	Qualitative and quantitative input of a diverse set of stakeholders across the entire FSC.	Tailoring policy briefs to the regional challenges to solve wicked, cross-stage problems.		S & G				S & G	S & G		
WP3	M30- M40	Discussing the policy implications of the UC results.			S & G							

4.3. Action Timeline

Due to the central role of the CoP for the PRECIOUS project, the timing of their implementation is critical to ensuring impact and alignment with project objectives. Figure 2 provides a visual overview of the project’s timeline for CoP Hosts, placing particularly the 5 planned CoP workshops on the timeline. Initial suggestions are included regarding the best timing to link specific PRECIOUS content and themes to enable timely and relevant feedback. WP and Task leaders are expected to pro-actively support the CoP Hosts and provide meaningful material and questions to discuss the most suitable time to include their topics in a CoP meeting.

This timeline serves as initial guidance. Since the trajectory of CoPs is co-shaped by members, additional meetings and topics can be integrated dynamically.

Figure 2: Action Timeline

4.4. Project Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input

To enhance the Mapping Table presented earlier in the CoP Governance Framework, this section shares further details on the best alignment of the CoPs with relevant work packages and project tasks. The discussed tasks are based on the Grant Agreement, as well as on collaborative discussions with all relevant work packages. For each mentioned project task, the subsequent sections provide an overview of the task’s objectives, its needs (e.g. qualitative or quantitative data, verification or feedback), and its value for the CoP participants. The latter includes an outlook on how integrating a certain task can serve the involved stakeholders in their own mission and trajectory towards FLWPR.

4.4.1. Alignment with WP3 – Use cases implementation

The Use Cases (UCs), operating under PRECIOUS WP3, have the purpose to test and evaluate novel practices to reduce FLW. The Spanish UC has a focus on the meat industry, particularly VEGALSA’s food supply chain, whereas the Greek UC focuses on vegetable and fruit products in the food supply chains of RIZES Greek Deli and FONTE DI VITA. The pilot testing and data generation under WP3 feed into work packages 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 and 7. Hence, the UCs are a core element of the PRECIOUS project. For further details on the implementation framework of the Use Cases, please refer to the Use Cases Implementation Framework (D3.1).

While the UCs are focused on the food supply chains, the CoPs have a wider scope beyond the individual supply chains. The CoPs build on the insights of the UCs and other WPs to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, dissemination of results, and the adoption of FLWPR practices by actors outside of the immediate supply chain of the UCs. Further, the CoPs provide a space to solve challenges across supply chain stages. By collaboratively solving cross-stage challenges, the CoPs aim to foster goal-oriented networks, contributing to regional change beyond the project's lifetime.

Table 3. Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input, WP3

Needs for Stakeholder Input (beyond the Use Cases)	Added Value for CoP Members
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding needs of stakeholders in relation to consumer behaviour change towards FLWPR beyond the use cases. • Collaborate with stakeholders that can create positive impact for consumer behaviour, including European sister projects • Develop solutions on FLWPR challenges through workshops and co-creation • Discussing the policy implications of the UC results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn from best practices and experiences developed in the UCs. • Scale up practices to decrease the overall FLW in the FSCs.

Timeline:

- Perform workshops or co-creation activities within the CoPs and/or with European event participations aiming to improve the uptake of FLWPR actions (M9-M40).
- Define the baseline and need for improvement through workshops and co-creation activities within CoP and/or European system projects in regard to consumer food waste behaviour change. (M20-M24).
- Collaboration with WP6 to enhance stakeholder acceptance of the actions undertaken for the food waste prevention governance strategy (M25-34).
- Perform workshop or co-creation activities within the CoP and/or European sister projects aim to develop solutions on FLWPR challenges in the FSC, including the consumer stage. (M26-M40)
- Integrating outputs into policy recommendations, linked to Task 5.5 and WP6 (M30-40).

4.4.2. Task 1.4 – Strategies to increase consumer acceptance for upcycled food products

Task 1.4, *Strategies to increase consumer acceptance for upcycled food products and lower the rebound effect*, aims to identify strategies to enhance consumer acceptance of upcycled food products and minimize social rebound effects, and encourage positive spillovers related to FLWPR. Through a scoping literature review and online quasi-experiments in Spain, Greece, and Germany, the task will assess acceptance levels and psychological barriers (e.g., trust, disgust, perceived risks). It will further explore the role of communication strategies and social norms in encouraging positive spillovers, with findings feeding into the modelling efforts in Task 1.5.

Table 4. Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input, T1.4

Needs for Stakeholder Input	Added Value for CoP Members
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with the entire CoP is not necessary. • acquiring local consumer insights in UC locations and Germany to provide context-specific understandings of consumer behaviors, perceptions, and barriers via quasi-experiments and interviews with a subset of the UCs stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.4 can provide context-specific insights into acceptance of upcycled food products at the consumer stage, a relevant challenge for both CoPs and CRNs. • The insights will help with addressing consumer barriers regarding upcycled food products, avoiding social rebound effects, and improving consumer-facing communication. • Supports identification of effective FLWPR actions, including spillover effect considerations, by investigating consumer responses and behavioral feedback loops. • It can contribute to the goal of creating FLWPR-related start-ups, thanks to stakeholders' actions in the CoP regions.

Timeline:

- T1.4 Duration: M4-M32
- D1.4 *Consumer acceptance report* Due Date M32 (year 3)

4.4.3. Task 5.1 & Task 5.2 – Sustainability Risk Assessment

Task 5.1, *Design a Sustainability Risk Assessment Framework (SRAF)* identifies, measures, assesses, and treats environmental, social, and economic risks related to FLWPR strategies. It combines quantitative tools and qualitative hotspot analyses to support evidence-based mitigation and adaptation strategies, considering potential rebound and trade-off effects. Task 5.2 *Apply the Risk Assessment Framework (SRAF)*, to scale up the results to real-world use cases and other EU projects to analyze risks, validate strategies, and identify key success factors. The insights gained will inform policy recommendations and are reported in Deliverable D5.1.

Table 5. Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input, T5.1 & T5.2

Stakeholder Input Needs	Added Value for CoP Members
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of needs and the potential applications for the risk assessment framework by the stakeholders. • Qualitative and quantitative input for the identification, weighting, and design of model parameters. • Operationalisation and validation of the model by a diverse set of stakeholders. • Testing the model by performing an LCA. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of a risk assessment framework tailored to stakeholders' needs and objectives. • Identification of sustainability risks • Development of a set framework to develop

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aim to have stakeholder input for the three target audiences: consumer, producers and supply chain actors, policy makers. | <p>consistent strategies for FLWPR.</p> |
|---|---|

Timeline:

- T5.1 Design a Sustainability Risk Assessment Framework (SRAF) Duration: M6-M24
- T5.2 Apply the Risk Assessment Framework (SRAF) Duration: M24-M46
- D5.1 Sustainability Risk Assessment Guide. Application to FLWPR actions Due Date M46 (year 4)
- D5.2 Key EU relevant emission reduction funding instruments and initiatives targeting FLWPR Due Date M46 (year 4)

4.4.4. Task 5.3 – Policy Design Framework

Task 5.3, *Develop a Comprehensive Policy Design Framework for the EU, Co-Designed with Stakeholders*, focuses on creating an EU-wide policy design framework for climate transition and FLWPR, developed collaboratively with stakeholders. It integrates major EU and national strategies (e.g., Green Deal, Farm to Fork, CAP, Food 2030) and policy instruments like carbon pricing and green subsidies. The task also maps how current EU directives are implemented across supply chains, identifying regulatory barriers and best practices. The results will inform scenario development and be reported in Deliverable D5.2.

Table 6. Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input, T5.3

Stakeholder Input Needs	Added Value for CoP Members
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the most significant points of loss in the local food supply chain (FSC). • Understand consumer behaviors that contribute to food loss and waste (FLW). • Detect policy gaps and regulatory barriers that hinder FLW reduction efforts. • Review existing food waste laws and evaluate their effectiveness and enforcement. • Assess the limitations stakeholders face (financial, operational, regulatory, etc.) and their level of commitment to FLW reduction. • Explore strategies for preserving food and extending shelf life. • Identify opportunities to revalue or upcycle by-products (e.g., turning surplus into new products). • Develop viable and scalable business models that support FLW prevention and reduction. • Provide reliable and relevant data to inform strategy development and decision-making. • Evaluate the environmental and social impacts of FLW across the FSC. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insights into consumer behavior and socioeconomic factors influencing FLW. • Strengthened consumer education to foster more sustainable consumption habits. • Tools to monitor and raise awareness of FLW in households. • Implementation of FLWPR actions tailored to stakeholder contexts. • Access to structured data and prioritization tools to support evidence-based decision-making. • In-depth analysis of regional FLW data to identify local trends and hotspots. • Enhanced ability to strategically plan interventions and prioritize actions based on data. • Identification and closure of infrastructure gaps in FLW management and valorization. • Investments in local processing infrastructure to support food recovery and reuse. • Improved access to EU and national funding opportunities for FLW initiatives. • Financial support for upcycling and revaluation of by-products. • Policy support and stronger enforcement of FLW-related action plans to ensure long-term impact.

Timeline:

- T5.3 Develop a Comprehensive Policy Design Framework for the EU, Co-Designed with Stakeholders, Duration M6-M48
- D5.3 Sustainable net-zero pathways in the EU integrating FLW strategies Due Date M44 (year 4)

4.4.5. Task 5.5 – Policy Recommendations

Task 5.5, Policy Recommendations, focuses on the development of policy advice from the local to the national and European scale. It builds on the outputs of the previous WP5 tasks and the insights of the Use Cases, CoPs and CRNs. The CoPs and CRNs play an essential role in validating the policy briefs, grounding the briefs towards the actual challenges of regional stakeholders in the FLWPR.

Table 7. Needs and Opportunities for Stakeholder Input, T5.5

Stakeholder Input Needs	Added Value for CoP Members
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative and quantitative input of a diverse set of stakeholders across the entire FSC. • Validation of the policy recommendations via surveys, questionnaires, or workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailoring policy briefs to the regional challenges to solve wicked, cross-stage problems.

Timeline:

- T5.5 Policy recommendations from the local to national and European scale, Duration M24-M48.
- D5.4 Policy Briefs, Due Date M46

5. Outlook

This document provides guidance on steering the CoP to simultaneously address the interest and needs of CoP members, while also delivering on the project's objectives and needs. To achieve a synergistic integration of both, it is important to stay dynamic and open to the co-creative nature of the CoP process. Hence, the CoP process will yield the best results if this guidance is adopted dynamically. This implies:

- CoP Hosts should use this guidance document as a starting point and reference manual, rather than a static framework.
- PRECIOUS project partners, especially task leaders with the need for stakeholder input, should take the CoP profiles into consideration and actively collaborate with CoP members for the development and design of their outputs.
- CoP members should be allowed to actively shape the trajectory of the CoPs and take co-ownership of the format, by adapting the methodology to their needs and requirements and to get the best value from it.

Looking ahead, the CoPs will play a crucial role in applying the project outputs in the specific regional contexts in Greece and Spain and enhancing the project outputs for further uptake nationally and on at the European level. By convening diverse stakeholders across the entire food supply chain, covering all stages fostering collaboration and co-creation of FLWPR actions, and addressing cross-stage challenges, the CoPs have the potential to foster long-lasting change that contributes to more sustainable food systems.

From summer 2025 onwards, the CoP Hosts CluBE and ASINCAR have the opportunity and responsibility to adapt this CoP governance framework into life. WP6 leader CSCP will support them by organizing one online Train-the-Trainer meeting to foster the uptake of the governance framework and to increase the skills and abilities of the local implementers. This work shall also serve as inspiration to the leads of the CRNs.

In month 18 of the project, the results achieved so far will be reviewed by the whole PRECIOUS consortium in an Impact Workshop. This will enable all partners to share knowledge and learn from one another, provide mutual support and take corrective actions when necessary.

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ANNEX 1 – CONVENING GUIDANCE & TOOLS

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CoP Engagement Decision and Entry Points

This section presents all earlier identified Engagement Decision Points and Engagement Entry Points from the [→Stakeholder Mapping](#) (D6.1.) for the convenience of the CoP Hosts. It is a starting point for agenda planning and discussion, open to further discussion. This section also contributes to the development of local ownership and collective impact for long-term collaboration ([→ Vision](#)) (Ch. 3.1)

Engagement Decision Points:

- Engagement Decision Points highlight challenges or aspects that require conscious consideration. These aspects will be jointly explored with the local partners given the project’s objectives and the local stakeholders’ interests, to co-create targeted and effective stakeholder engagement in the PRECIOUS project.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Engagement Entry Points highlight opportunities to connect with stakeholders. These entry points can serve as a base for further engagement steps in the PRECIOUS project.

A. Greek CoP

Engagement Decision Points:

- In an effort to contribute to the educational campaigns related to FLWPR (Task 7.5), suitable educational centres will need to be identified and the material will need to be tailored to the target audience. It should be discussed to what extent the CoPs can support or facilitate this process.
- The alignment of the UC activities (WP3) and the CoP (WP6) will further need to be developed, in order to use synergies between both formats.

Stakeholder Composition

Engagement Decision Points:

- The **food services stage** and the **household stage** are currently not represented in the stakeholder mapping in the Greece CoP. To tackle it, especially the challenge of **limited public awareness** and **deeply rooted cultural habits** around food consumption, it may be worth integrating stakeholders from this sector.
- At the moment, the household sector has not been included. Looking at the contextual challenges of a traditional food culture, the question arises whether involving the household sector in the CoP might be beneficial. **Whether and how to include household-stage stakeholders** will need to be discussed in collaboration with the Task 1.4 leads.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under Work Package (WP) 5 and Task 1.4, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The high stakeholder count in the processing and manufacturing stage can provide a good basis for the stakeholder engagement, if the CoP’s scope is set accordingly.

Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

Engagement Decision Points:

- The current influence and interest ratings seem rather high across all stakeholder categories, which indicates a significant bias, either in the selection or ranking of the stakeholders. As a result, a selection of stakeholders based on the interest and influence rating would likely result in a suboptimal consortium.

- Relying on food waste prevention engagement rankings and categorizations of how the business model is affected by FLWPR will yield more reliable insights on which stakeholders should be engaged.

Relations to Mapped Stakeholders

Engagement Decision Points:

- To drive regional change towards reduced food loss and waste, intensifying the connection to regional and local stakeholders will prove valuable. Designing the engagement approach to cater to these two groups will be essential.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Making use of the good international and European relations can be useful for the objectives of the PRECIOUS project and should therefore be built upon.
- Building on existing relations of the local host can provide an entry point for the recruitment of further stakeholders with similar interests.

Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups

Engagement Decision Points:

- It will be relevant to **decide early on which aspects the CoP wants to focus on**. The motivators and barriers can provide support in aligning the CoP's scope with the interests of the stakeholders and create the right engagement incentives.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Using the **cross-stage learning and exchange, corporate social responsibility, and financial benefits as main arguments** will be most convincing for stakeholders to participate in the CoP.
- Simultaneously, different arguments should be put to the foreground in communication, **depending on the stakeholder's FSC stage and current FLWPR engagement**.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

Engagement Decision Points:

- It will be relevant to **decide early on which aspects the Greek CoP wants to focus on**. The motivators and barriers can provide support in aligning the CoP's scope with the interests of the stakeholders.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Designing the stakeholder engagement to **address the financial concerns** and make a compelling argument for the increased economic efficiency of reduced FLW will encourage more stakeholders to join the Greek CoP.
- Highlighting the CoP's ability to enable **cross-stage knowledge exchange** will be a great opportunity to engage more stakeholders.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

B. Spanish CoP

Engagement Decision Points:

- In an effort to contribute to the educational campaigns related to FLWPR (Task 7.5), suitable educational centres will need to be identified and the material will need to be tailored to the target audience. It should be discussed to what extent the CoPs can support or facilitate this process.
- Further, in an effort to contribute to the communication of actions and results under Task 3.3, it will be helpful to engage further stakeholders along the FSC to replicate and increase the scope of the UC. Whether and how the CoP can support this objective should be discussed by UC leads, task leads, and potentially the CoP participants.

Stakeholder Composition

Engagement Decision Points:

- At the moment, the household sector has not been included. Looking at the contextual challenges of a traditional food culture, the question arises whether involving the household sector in the CoP might be beneficial? **Whether and how to include household-stage stakeholders** can be discussed in collaboration with the Task 1.4 leads.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under WP5 and Task 1.4, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.
- Which stakeholders to involve will depend on the CoP's scope, which the local host will have to determine in collaboration with project partners, project objectives, and a view on the needs of the mapped stakeholders.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The current focus on **stakeholders of the processing and manufacturing stage** provides a potential entry point for the recruitment, if the CoP's scope is decided on respectively.

Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

Engagement Decision Points:

- The **cross-stage dependence of impactful stakeholders** could be leveraged as an effective motivator for the engagement.
- **Focusing on the stakeholders in the “manage closely” quadrant** already provides a diverse set of stakeholders. At the same time, some of the more influential stakeholders and cross-stage dependent stakeholders fall into the “keep satisfied” quadrant. While generally the recommendation is to focus on the stakeholders in the “manage closely” quadrant, it can be discussed whether some of the stakeholders of the “keep satisfied” quadrant should be included as well.
- It may be worth including cross-stage dependent stakeholders from other quadrants.

Relations to Mapped Stakeholders

Engagement Decision Points:

- Simultaneously, by clearly **defining the scope of the CoP**, it will be easier to select which stakeholders to recruit in regards of supply chain stages and geographical scope.

Engagement Entry Points:

- **Building on the well-established ties** to various stakeholders is an opportunity to ease the recruitment process for the CoP.

Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups

Engagement Decision Points:

- When defining the scope of the CoP, the motivators, barriers, and project objectives should be taken into consideration.
- It is to be discussed which PRECIOUS technological solutions could be of interest to the Spanish stakeholders in view of the motivators and challenges.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Tailoring the **arguments towards the specific key motivators of each supply chain stage** will be helpful to engage stakeholders. The strategy can be similar for both, less and more engaged actors.
- PRECIOUS-related redistribution content could be tested particularly well in Spain.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

Engagement Decision Points:

- When defining the scope of the CoP, the motivators, barriers, and project objectives should be taken into consideration.
- For food banks, humanitarian organizations, and research centres already working on food waste, it will be necessary to further understand potential barriers for their engagement in PRECIOUS activities.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Designing the stakeholder engagement process to meet the specific barriers of concerns regarding **uneconomical** actions, increasing **consumer acceptance**, and identifying **pathways to reduce FLW while complying with product safety standards** will provide a compelling set of arguments to actors who are not yet intrinsically engaged.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives. The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

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ANNEX 2 – COLLABORATION GUIDANCE & TOOLS

PRECIOUS

Declaration of Participation Template

The following draft document serves as a starting point for the Community of Practice on stakeholder engagement. It is an illustrative example and will be adapted and rewritten by the CoP Hosts, before discussion with the CoP members, based on the specific context, stakeholders, and goals of each CoP.

Community of Practice (CoP): Terms of Reference and Code of Conduct

1. Vision

The PRECIOUS Community of Practice (CoP) in Greece / Spain serves as a participatory and collaborative platform for stakeholders across the food supply chain to co-create solutions, exchange knowledge, and foster innovation towards Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction (FLWPR). This CoP aims to enhance PRECIOUS findings and to foster the uptake of stakeholder driven, locally relevant and context-specific strategies to reduce food loss and waste.

2. Objectives

- Promote knowledge exchange and mutual learning among stakeholders.
- Co-develop and adapt FLWPR solutions to local contexts.
- Foster multi-stakeholder collaboration to support impactful and actionable outcomes.
- Support the uptake of FLWPR-related policies, innovations, and business models.

3. Scope and Membership

- The CoP includes participants from diverse sectors: producers, processors, retailers, consumers, policymakers, civil society, academia, and startups.
- Membership is voluntary and open to any stakeholder committed to the objectives of the CoP.
- Members are encouraged to participate actively, share experiences, and support collective goals.

4. Roles and Responsibilities

- **ASINCAR / CluBE as Facilitator(s):** Guide discussions, manage meetings, and maintain a safe, inclusive environment.
- **TBD Core Group:** Provide strategic direction, co-shape agendas, and foster community cohesion.
- **Members:** Participate in at least 3 meetings, best all CoP meetings. Contribute to discussions, share knowledge, and co-create outputs.
- **PRECIOUS Consortium as Supporters:** Providing input, guidance and support on FLWPR as well as stakeholder engagement.

5. Meetings and Activities

- The CoP will meet regularly (minimum of five times throughout the PRECIOUS project duration).
- Activities may include workshops, TBD thematic discussions, site visits, collaborative prototyping, and feedback sessions.
- Meetings may be held in physical, hybrid or virtual formats, based on participant needs.

6. Code of Conduct

To ensure a respectful, inclusive, and constructive environment, all members agree to:

- Treat each other with respect and courtesy.
- Listen actively and acknowledge diverse perspectives.
- Share knowledge openly while respecting confidentiality when applicable.
- Avoid discriminatory, offensive, or disruptive behavior.
- Foster a collaborative and problem-solving attitude.
- Declare any conflicts of interest when relevant to discussions.

Breaches of conduct may result in facilitation-led mediation or, in serious cases, withdrawal from the CoP.

7. Confidentiality and Attribution

- While openness is encouraged, sensitive or unpublished information shared in confidence should not be disseminated without permission.
- Collaborative outputs may be attributed collectively unless specific contributions are individually identified.

8. Review and Adaptation

These Terms of Reference and Code of Conduct will be reviewed annually or as needed, based on community feedback and evolving needs.

PRECIOUS

Planning and Running a CoP Session

Effectively engaging stakeholders is a dynamic and iterative process that requires careful planning, clear objectives, and continuous adaptation. This section builds on the key steps identified under the [→Stakeholder Mapping](#) (D6.1.), providing additional and practice-oriented guidance for each key question.

Time line	Meeting frequency	Objective of the activity	Description of engagement needs	Stakeholder groups to be engaged	Benefit for the stakeholder	Envisioned engagement formats	Follow-up activities
		Please briefly state the objective of the activity. What do you hope to achieve/what outcome are you envisioning from this activity?	Please state briefly what your engagement needs are and WHY you need to engage stakeholders.	Please list all stakeholder groups that should be engaged.	What will the stakeholders get out of the engagement (e.g. insights, exchange, visibility, etc.).	Consider the level of engagement (inform, consult, collaborate, etc.) Consider the engagement format (interview, workshop, etc.)	Consider which follow-up activities are needed, e.g. sharing the recording of a webinar, etc.
The WHEN		THE WHY		The WHO		The HOW	What's NEXT
 6							

1

The WHY**Defining the scope & objectives of your CoP meeting**

What would you like to achieve with the meeting?

In the context of PRECIOUS, each Community of Practice (CoP) meeting is a unique opportunity to advance the project's aim of reducing food loss and its environmental impacts. This step focuses on defining the specific scope and objectives of your CoP meeting, tailored to the needs of each country and the stakeholder ecosystem. Clearly articulated objectives will help shape all other steps, from participant selection to facilitation tools.

Checklist

- Define the overarching goal and specific objectives of the CoP meeting. Keep in mind how many meetings (min. 5) you have planned and think through what you need to do when in order to manage everything you need. Prioritise.
- The first meeting will be key to set a common goal for the group in line with the overall PRECIOUS [→Vision](#) (Ch. 3.1). You will also need to consider and discuss [→Governance](#) and [→Leadership](#) (Ch. 3.2. and 3.3.).
- Align with PRECIOUS' key focus areas (e.g. food loss prevention, rebound effects, environmental data use) [→CoP Engagement Decision and Entry Points](#) (Annex 1).
- Brainstorm with local partners and the CSCP to develop the focus of your meeting, remember the [→Mapping thematic and regional needs and opportunities](#) (Ch. 4.2.).
- Draft a preliminary agenda based on agreed objectives.

Bright Notes

- Ensure objectives align with PRECIOUS' ambition to co-create impactful, systems-level solutions
- Consider national food system priorities and stakeholder dynamics
- Adjust to local needs while maintaining coherence with project-wide goals
- Remember that the goal is to learn from each other and involve multiple levels of stakeholders to create the best solutions [\(→ Collaboration and Cooperation\)](#) (Ch. 3.5).

2

THE WHO

Identifying key stakeholders to engage in your CoP meeting & setting a timeframe**Who should be part of the meeting?**

Each PRECIOUS CoP meeting benefits from a diverse and relevant group of participants. In certain circumstances, however, specific sensitive topics are also best discussed in a smaller, more confidential circle. Stakeholders may include actors from farming, food processing, retail, policy, research, and civil society. Identifying the right participants ensures rich dialogue and actionable outcomes.

Checklist

- Build on the [→Stakeholder Mapping](#) (D.6.1.) to identify key participants relevant for the topic. Who is influential? Who impacted? Who is interested in proactive engagement? Consider if a topic might be sensitive to some partners which might limit the likelihood for free expressions.
- Consider what timing and mode of meeting would be most promising to attract the relevant stakeholder. ([→Convening](#) (Ch. 3.4.).)
- Exchange with local partners and the CSCP to refine your list.
- Reach out to stakeholders via email or phone to inform and invite them. Balance formal and informal outreach methods based on context and on your impression on how to best attract the relevant stakeholder.
- Identify suitable leaders (best senior or middle managers) that will be active and drive the process, or create visibility and outreach opportunities.

Bright Notes

- Clearly communicate stakeholders' important role in shaping solutions
- Update your stakeholder mapping as new actors emerge

3

The WHEN**Format & duration of the CoP meeting**

When & where are you planning to hold your CoP meeting?

Once the scope, participants, and objectives are clear, it's time to determine when and how to hold the CoP. Whether in-person or online, design your meeting to foster meaningful interaction and collaboration.

Checklist

- Decide on format (online or face-to-face) and duration (e.g. 2 hours to full day) – discuss and decide how to create the best possible space for the meeting ([→Convening](#)) (Ch. 3.4.).
- Develop a preliminary agenda with input from partners
- Send a save-the-date email (6–4 weeks in advance)
- Book venue and catering (if applicable)
- Choose and test digital tools if online

Bright Notes

- Consider stakeholder availability when setting duration and time. Useful to have at least first and last meeting physically. Alternating online meetings may support discussions of urgent issues and also the participation of more participants.
- Keep online platforms user-friendly and accessible.
- Test equipment and tools in advance to avoid technical hiccups

4

The HOW**Preparing the CoP meeting**

Has everything been prepared properly?

This is the final planning stage before your CoP meeting takes place. Finalize agendas, coordinate with facilitators, and ensure all materials and technical tools are ready. Integrating storytelling and interactive elements can help align stakeholders around a shared vision.

Checklist

- Send reminder email (and in case of online meeting the registration link) to participants
- Finalize agenda and internal working plan (moderation, roles, materials)
- Plan for interactive sessions and sufficient breaks → Interactive Methods Descriptions (Annex 2).
- Develop a feedback form → Participant survey and Feedback Survey Templates (Annex 3).
- Brief the facilitation team → Meeting Report Template (Annex 3) and Participant List Template (Annex 2).
- Prepare logistics and technical setup

Bright Notes

- Make breaks purposeful (for networking and informal exchange)
- Include storytelling as a way to connect different perspectives
- Ensure the engagement of multi level stakeholders to enable co-development of the solutions and learn from one another → Collaboration and Cooperation (Ch. 3.5.)

5

Let's ENGAGE

The day of the CoP meeting

Let's run it!

Now it's time to bring everything together. Ensure participants feel welcomed, the agenda flows smoothly, and discussions are captured effectively. Facilitate inclusively and adapt flexibly when needed.

Checklist

- Arrive early to set up (or log in early if online)
- Welcome participants and introduce the meeting
- Ensure →Participant list and →Consent forms are signed (both Annex 2)
- Capture key discussion points and action items
- Use photos and social media to share highlights
- Run a quick feedback session at the end

Bright Notes

- Be flexible: allow room for discussions to evolve
- Create a safe space where all voices are heard
- Share ownership with participants to build lasting engagement
- Put emphasis on learning from one another during the session, including all the participants → Collaboration and Cooperation (Ch. 3.5.)

6

What's NEXT**Following up**

The meeting took place, so what's next?

Post-meeting follow-up is essential to maintain momentum and translate discussions into actions. Keep stakeholders engaged by sharing outcomes and involving them in next steps, both in the CoP and the broader PRECIOUS project.

Checklist

- Send a thank-you email with presentations, recordings (if applicable), and next steps
- Share the link to the feedback form again
- Transcribe and organize notes and action points
- Share outcomes with partners and participants
- Plan upcoming activities based on CoP results
- Fill out the “Summary of the CoP meeting” → [Meeting Report Template \(Annex 3\)](#)
- Meet with the CSCP and partners to debrief
- Share results on social media and, if possible, in local media

Bright Notes

- Follow-up quickly: memories fade fast!
- Encourage participants to share materials within their networks
- Use feedback to refine the format for future meetings

PRECIOUS

Meeting Script Template

Details of CoP meeting

Date / Time	
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please list the purposes of your session here
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please list the (groups of) participants here
Location	
Language	
Format	In person / online
Organizer	

Meeting Agenda and Facilitation (including sample text)

Time	Point/Topic What to discuss?	Method How to discuss?	Materials What is needed?	Facilitating roles
XX	1. Welcome and Introductions	Speech/ no special method	-	1. Facilitator 2. Maybe another speaker who welcomes participants
XX	2. PRECIOUS project	1. Presentation 2. Questions & Answers (Q&A) – Ask participants if they have questions	Meeting presentation	3. Facilitator 4. Time keeper
XX		→Interactive Methods Descriptions (Annex 2)		
XX				
XX	7. Summary and Take Away's	Possibility to note down key take away's on a flipchart (or digitally in the presentation)	Maybe: Flipchart + Marker	1. Facilitator 2. Someone who notes down key take away's

PRECIOUS

Interactive Methods Descriptions

In this section, several potential interactive methods are presented, that can be used in the CoP activities depending on the respective objective. Each method is shortly described, followed by an overview as well as a step-by-step implementation guide. CoP Hosts are invited to choose from this catalogue. You will find:

- Brainstorming & Affinity Mapping
- Dot voting
- Conversation Starters
- Worldcafé
- Fishbowl Discussion
- Stakeholder Role Play
- SWOT Analysis
- Action Plan Development

A. Brainstorming & Affinity Mapping

Brainstorming is a creative technique designed to generate a wide range of ideas on a specific topic within a short period. Participants are encouraged to think freely and suggest ideas without immediate evaluation or criticism, fostering an open and inclusive environment. This method is effective for both small and larger groups.

Following brainstorming, Affinity Mapping (also known as Affinity Diagramming) is employed to organise the generated ideas. Participants group similar ideas into clusters based on their natural relationships, which helps in diagnosing complex situations and identifying common themes. This structured approach aids in making sense of extensive data and is particularly useful for larger groups.

Overview

Element	Details
General Objective	To generate a diverse set of ideas in an open and inclusive environment and systematically organise them into meaningful clusters, enabling participants to identify patterns, common themes, and key insights.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	Brainstorming to gather insights from stakeholders on their preferred ways of involvement and contributions to the CoP. Affinity mapping to categorise and structure these inputs and to align them with the CoP context.
Time Needed	30 – 70 min (flexible based on group size and level of detail).
Number of Participants	4 – 50 people; split people in groups of 4-6 per flip chart/ pin board/ virtual break out session.
Materials	Sticky notes (various colours), large flipcharts/ pin boards/ virtual pin boards like MIRO/MURAL etc., markers, printed project goals for reference, tape or board for clustering insights, stickers for optional prioritization.
Moderators	1-2 facilitators to guide discussions, encourage participation, and help with clustering ideas.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (5-10 min)

- Briefly introduce the objective of the session:
“Today, we want to hear directly from you – [participants] – about how you see your role in the Communities of Practice. Your input will help shape how we work together.”
- Provide a quick refresher on the project goals and previously discussed insights to set the stage.
- Explain the method:
 - We’ll start with an open brainstorming session.
 - Then, we’ll group similar ideas together to identify key themes (Affinity Mapping).
 - Finally, we’ll discuss and refine the ideas collectively.

2. Individual & Group Brainstorming (10-20 min)

- Give each participant sticky notes and markers.
- Ask them to write down their thoughts individually (one idea per sticky note) to reply to these questions:
 1. How would you like to be involved in the Communities of Practice?
 2. What specific skills, resources, or expertise can you contribute?
(note: you can specify this question if specific contributions are needed)
- 5 minutes before the group work ends, participants share their ideas within their groups (4-6 people).
- Groups place all their sticky notes on a shared flipchart or board for visibility.

3. Affinity Mapping – Organising Ideas (5-10 min)

- Facilitators help the groups cluster similar ideas together into broad themes (e.g., knowledge sharing, practical fieldwork, policy engagement, funding needs).
- Label each group of ideas with a category title that reflects the main theme.
- If needed, ask participants to help refine or merge overlapping ideas.

4. Group Discussion & Refinement (10-20 min)

- Once the themes are clear, open the floor for discussion:
 1. Do these categories make sense?
 2. Are there any missing perspectives?
 3. What seems most important or feasible?
- Optional: Use dot voting (each participant gets a few stickers to place on the themes they consider most relevant or urgent).
- Facilitators document key insights to ensure they are considered in the next steps of the project.

5. Closing & Linking to Next Steps (5-10 min)

- Summarise the main themes and priorities identified.
- Explain how these insights will be used to structure the Action Plan session.
- Thank participants and encourage them to stay engaged in the next phases of the project.

B. Dot Voting

Dot Voting, also known as "multi-voting" or "dotmocracy," is a facilitation method used to prioritise options or make collective decisions. Participants are given a set number of stickers or dots and place them next to the options they prefer. The options with the most dots are considered the group's priorities. This technique is simple, transparent, and effective for both small and large groups.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To help participants quickly prioritise solutions or ideas by voting with dots, ensuring democratic decision-making.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	To prioritise the solutions that ought to be tested in the CoP. Solutions can have been previously developed in co-creation, discussed in a World Café format, or suggested by CoP partners.
Time Needed	15 – 30 minutes (depending on the number of options and participants).
Number of Participants	unlimited
Materials	Sticky dots (or markers for manual voting), flipcharts or posters with ideas listed, tape or board for displaying options. Can also be virtual dots on a shared PowerPoint/MIRO/MURAL in virtual co-creation sessions.
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to explain the process, ensure clarity of options, and count votes.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Instructions (3 – 10 min)

- Introduce the purpose of the voting:
“We will now prioritise the solutions or ideas that resonate most with the group, helping us focus on what’s most important moving forward.”
- Explain the dot voting process:
 - Each participant gets a set number of dots (e.g., 3-5 per person).
 - They place their dots on the ideas they find most relevant or important.
 - They can put multiple dots on one idea if they feel strongly about it.
 - The idea(s) with the most dots will be prioritised for further discussion or action.

2. Voting Process (7 – 15 min)

- Participants move around and place their dots on the listed ideas.
- Facilitators monitor the process, ensuring everyone participates and understands the system.

3. Review & Next Steps (5 min)

- Facilitators count the dots and highlight the top-voted ideas.
- Explain how these results will inform the next workshop steps.
- Thank participants for their input before transitioning to the next activity.

C. Conversation Starters

Conversation Starters are prompts or questions designed to initiate dialogue on specific topics. They serve to spark discussion, encourage participants to share perspectives, and delve deeper into subjects. This method is versatile and can be adapted for both small and large groups, depending on the context and objectives.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To initiate meaningful discussions and encourage participants to share perspectives by using prompts that spark dialogue and deepen engagement with the topic.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	To spark open conversations on key aspects of the CoPs, encouraging participants to share their thoughts and experiences without the pressure of reaching conclusions. Facilitators take notes to capture key discussion points.
Time Needed	15 – 45 minutes (depending on the number of questions discussed).
Number of Participants	4 – 24 people; ideally 8-16 participants in total, or groups of 6-8 people.
Materials	(Printed) conversation starter cards, a timer for rotations, and notebooks or digital tools for facilitators to take notes.
Moderators	1 – 3 facilitators to introduce the method, monitor discussions, and take notes.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (3 min)

- Introduce the purpose of the session:

“This session is all about sparking conversation on [e.g. the planned experiments in the Communities of Practice]. There are no right or wrong answers—just an opportunity to exchange ideas and perspectives.”
- Explain the method:
 - Facilitator asks thought-provoking questions (prompts) tailored to the goals of the session and shows them to participants (e.g., on a slide or a printed card).
 - Participants note down their thoughts on the question.
 - After everybody had time to think about the question, participants share their thoughts.
 - There is no need to reach a conclusion—just engage in conversation. All thoughts are welcome.
 - Facilitators will take notes on key discussion points (in each group).
 - Once the time is up, a new thought-provoking question (prompt) is discussed.
- Alternative: Participants can also be split up in smaller groups and each group discusses one question which is provided to them as a print-out. After each group discussion, groups can rotate to discuss other questions.

2. Discussion of conversation starter questions (approx. 7 min per question)

- Setup: (Printed) conversation starter questions are asked to participants (either one question after another to the whole group; or different questions to different groups of participants).
- Examples for conversation starter questions:
 - What do you think is the most important goal of a Community of Practice?
 - We are thinking of implementing [describe solution/experiment]. What opportunities [or challenges, risks] do you associate with this?
 - What changes have you observed in food waste prevention and management over the years?
- Process:
 - A question is discussed for 5-10 minutes.
 - Facilitators take notes on emerging themes, interesting perspectives, or points of debate.
 - A facilitator signals when time is up.
 - The next question is discussed for 5-10 minutes, notes are taken and the facilitator signals time is up.
 - Continue this process until all questions have been discussed.
 - If participants were split up into groups: Groups rotate to a new table after the discussion of each question and engage with a new question.

3. Wrap-Up (5 min, optional)

- Once all questions have been discussed, the facilitator thanks participants and briefly acknowledges the richness of the discussions.
- Facilitators ensure that the notes collected will be available for later reference in the workshop.
- The session transitions into the next activity without a formal summary.

D. World Café

The World Café is a structured conversational process intended to facilitate open and intimate discussions, and link ideas within a larger group to access the collective intelligence. Participants split into smaller groups and discuss a topic at several tables, with individuals switching tables periodically and introducing their previous discussion to the new table. This method is particularly effective for larger groups (more than 15 people) and aims to improve large-group discussion through informal café-style conversations.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To facilitate a structured in-depth discussion on key topics by rotating participants across different tables, ensuring diverse perspectives and knowledge exchange. Table facilitators take notes to capture key insights.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	To facilitate in-depth discussions on potential solutions that can be tested in the CoP by assigning each table a specific FLWPR action, allowing participants to explore its feasibility, benefits, and implementation strategies through rotating conversations and collective knowledge exchange.
Time Needed	45 – 120 mins (depending on the number of tables and depth of discussion).
Number of Participants	15 – 50 people, ideally in small groups of 5-8 per table.
Materials	Large sheets of paper/ flip charts/ pin boards (one for each table), markers, sticky notes, printed guiding questions, timer for rotations. Can also be virtual pin boards like MIRO/MURAL etc. in virtual co-creation sessions.
Moderators	1 facilitator to introduce the method and monitor the discussions. Each table also has a table host (either a participant or a moderator) who stays to guide new arrivals.

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Context Setting (5-10 min)

- Introduce the purpose of the session:
“In this session, we will have rotating discussions on key topics related to [e.g. possible solutions to be tested in our CoP]. You will contribute your perspectives and build upon the ideas of others.”
- Explain the process:
 - There are different tables, each with a specific topic/question.
 - Participants rotate between tables, engaging in multiple discussions.
 - A table host remains at each table to facilitate table discussions and to summarise previous discussions for newcomers.
 - Facilitators will take notes on key insights emerging across tables.
Alternative: Participants document discussion results on discussion paper/ flipchart/ pin board.

2. Discussion Rounds (3 – 4 rounds of 10 – 20 min each; 30 – 90 min total)

- Round 1: Each group sits at a table and starts discussing the assigned topic, using the large sheet of paper/ flipchart/ pin board to capture key ideas.
- Rotation: After the time is up, participants move to a new table (except for the table host). The host briefly summarises the previous discussion before the new round begins.
- Repeating the process: Each group builds on the conversation from previous participants, deepening the discussion.
- Main facilitator moves around to observe and take notes on recurring themes.

3. Summary of Results (10 – 20 min)

- After the last rotation, table hosts sum up the ideas discussed at their table.
 - What common themes emerged?
 - Were there any surprising insights?
 - What ideas feel the most relevant or actionable?
- The session transitions into the next workshop activity.

E. Fishbowl Discussion

The Fishbowl Discussion is a format that promotes inclusive dialogue and active listening. A small group of participants engages in a discussion in an inner circle (the "fishbowl"), while the remaining participants observe from an outer circle. Observers can join the discussion by replacing someone in the fishbowl, allowing for dynamic participation. This method is effective for medium-sized and large groups and encourages deep, focused conversations.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To foster inclusive and dynamic discussions by allowing participants to engage in a focused conversation while others observe and listen, promoting active reflection, diverse input, and deeper exploration of key topics.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	To critically assess and refine tested FLWPR actions by facilitating a structured discussion where key stakeholders share their experiences in the inner circle, while others listen, reflect, and contribute new insights, ensuring the solutions are adapted for greater feasibility and impact.
Time Needed	45 – 60 minutes
Number of Participants	15 – 40 people (5-8 active participants at a time, others observing)
Materials	5 – 8 chairs arranged in an inner circle (for speakers) and outer circle (for observers), a guiding question, and a timer
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to introduce the topic, ensure smooth transitions, and capture key insights

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Setup (5-10 min)

- The facilitator explains the purpose of the Fishbowl:
“This method allows for focused discussion while encouraging active listening. A small group will discuss and evaluate [e.g. the results of the first round of experiments in our CoP] while others observe. Observers can join the conversation by swapping places.”
- Arrange seating:
 - The inner circle (5-8 seats) is for active discussants.
 - The outer circle is for observers who listen and take notes.
- Introduce the discussion prompt (e.g.: Based on the solutions tested so far, what have been the key successes and challenges in implementation? How can we adjust or improve these solutions to enhance their effectiveness, scalability, and adoption?).

2. Fishbowl Discussion (30-40 min)

- First Round (10-20 min):
 - Inner circle participants discuss the topic.
 - Outer circle listens, taking notes on key points.
- Swapping Participants (10-20 min):
 - Observers can tap a participant on the shoulder to swap seats and join the discussion.
 - The conversation continues with fresh perspectives.

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (approx.10 min)

- The facilitator asks e.g.,
 - What were the most compelling points raised?
 - Did any perspectives change through listening?
 - What should we take forward from this discussion?
- Facilitators summarise insights before moving to the next session.

F. Stakeholder Role-Playing

Stakeholder Role-Playing involves participants adopting the roles of various stakeholders relevant to a particular issue or project. By simulating these perspectives, participants gain empathy and a deeper understanding of different viewpoints, which can inform strategy development and decision-making. This method is suitable for small to medium-sized groups, depending on the number of stakeholder roles identified.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective	To enhance empathy and refine strategies by having participants take on different stakeholder roles (e.g., farmers, retail, policymakers, researchers) and discuss FLWPR actions from their assigned perspective.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	To explore the feasibility and impact of FLWPR actions by having participants role-play key stakeholders, enabling them to identify potential conflicts, synergies, and implementation ideas from multiple perspectives.
Time Needed	60 – 90 minutes
Number of Participants	15 – 36 people, working in small groups of 3-6.
Materials	Role description cards, scenario sheets, flipcharts, markers, and optional props to represent roles. Can also be done virtually (groups prepare in virtual break-out rooms and share their perspectives in main room).
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to provide support to group preparations and role plays

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Setup (10 min)

- Welcome participants and introduce the goal:
“Today, you will step into the shoes of different stakeholders involved in the food value chain. By discussing solutions from their perspectives, we can identify challenges, opportunities, and points of collaboration.”
- Explain the process:
 - Each group will receive a role card describing a stakeholder (e.g., farmer, researcher, policymaker, retail employee, environmental activist).
 - A scenario sheet presents a FLWPR solution to discuss from their assigned perspective.

2. Role-Playing Discussions (40-60 min)

- Group Discussions (20-30 min):
 - Participants stay in character and discuss how their stakeholder would view the problem, the challenges they face, and what solutions they support.
 - They note key points on flipcharts.
 - Facilitators move between groups, prompting deeper reflections.
- Group Sharing (approx. 5 min per group; in total 20-30 min):
 - Each group presents their stakeholder’s position.
 - Facilitators highlight patterns, differences, and surprising insights.

3. Reflection & Wrap-Up (10-15 min)

- The facilitator asks e.g.,
 - What perspectives were most surprising?
 - Where were the biggest conflicts or areas of alignment?
 - How can we use this understanding to improve the solution to be tested in the CoP?
- Key takeaways are summarised before transitioning to the next session.

G. SWOT Analysis

SWOT Analysis is a structured method that helps participants assess and refine FLWPR solutions at different stages of the co-creation process. By identifying Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, stakeholders can evaluate influencing factors, assess potential or tested solutions, refine implementation strategies, and anticipate future challenges. This method promotes a balanced discussion by considering both internal and external aspects, supporting informed decision-making and the continuous improvement of solutions. This method is effective for small and medium-sized groups.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To support the development and refinement of solutions by systematically assessing their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions, improve strategies, and enhance the long-term impact of the initiative.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	To evaluate a FLWPR tested in the CoP by identifying its Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, providing a structured foundation for decision-making.
Time Needed	60 – 90 minutes
Number of Participants	6 – 20 people, working in small groups of 5 – 6
Materials	Large SWOT matrix sheets, markers, sticky notes, and printed prompts to guide analysis. Can also be done virtually (groups prepare in virtual break-out rooms on a virtual pin board with a SWOT matrix and share their results in main room).
Moderators	1 – 2 facilitators to introduce the method, guide discussions, and help refine insights

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Set-up (10 min)

- The facilitator introduces the goal:
“We will systematically analyse a FLWPR solution, identifying its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This will help us to further refine it in the Community of Practice.”
- Explain the SWOT framework:
 - Strengths – What are the internal advantages or positive aspects of this solution that contribute to its success or effectiveness?
 - Weaknesses – What limitations, challenges, or areas for improvement exist within this solution?
 - Opportunities – What external factors, trends, or conditions could enhance the success or impact of this solution?
 - Threats – What external risks, obstacles, or barriers could hinder the success or implementation of this solution?
- Divide participants into small teams, each working on a specific FLWPR solution.

2. SWOT Analysis in Teams (40 – 50 min)

- Step 1: Brainstorming (20 – 30 min)
 - Teams write down their ideas for each category using sticky notes and placing them in the SWOT matrix.
 - Facilitators move around, prompting deeper analysis.
- Step 2: Refining & Prioritising (15 – 20 min)
 - Each team clusters their points into key themes per SWOT matrix field
 - They highlight the most critical insights in each category (key strengths, key weaknesses, key opportunities, key challenges).

3. Sharing & Discussion (15 – 20 min)

- Each team presents their SWOT matrix to the larger group.
- Facilitators help connect common insights across teams.
- The discussion focuses on:
 - How can we leverage strengths and opportunities?
 - How can we mitigate weaknesses and threats?
- Facilitators summarise key takeaways before transitioning to the next session.

SWOT Matrix Template

<p>Strengths What are the internal advantages of this solution?</p>	<p>Weaknesses What limitations/ challenges exist within the solution?</p>
<p>Opportunities What external factors could enhance success?</p>	<p>Threats What external risks or barriers could hinder success?</p>

H. Action Plan Development

Action Plan Development is a process where participants outline the steps necessary to achieve specific goals or implement solutions. This involves defining tasks that need to be done to reach an objective, assigning responsibilities for implementing the tasks, determining required resources, setting timelines, and identifying potential risks. Developing an action plan provides a clear roadmap for execution and accountability. This method can be used by groups of different sizes.

Overview

Element	Details
Objective (general)	To promote the adoption of sustainable FLWPR practices and make a real impact in reducing FLW and associated GHG emissions.
Sample Objective in PRECIOUS	Increase the sale of upcycled food products by 20% year to year.
Time Needed	2 – 3 hours (adjustable based on depth of discussion; can be shortened by focusing solely on selected aspects of the action plan).
Number of Participants	6 – 24 people; larger groups to be split up in mixed stakeholder sub-groups (4 – 6 per sub-group).
Materials	Printed Action Plan Templates, markers, sticky notes (various colours). Can also be done virtually on a virtual pin board with an Action Plan Template.
Moderators	2 facilitators to guide discussions

Step-by-Step Implementation

1. Introduction & Linking to Previous Activities (15-20 min)

- Recap Key Insights: Briefly summarise the outcomes of previous activities that inform the action plan. Highlight key decisions already made (e.g., the chosen solution, identified challenges, stakeholder insights).
- Set the Context: Explain that this session will focus on defining who does what next to bring the solution to life in real-world testing and scaling.
- Specify following aspects of the action plan template (please see template below)
 - Focus area, Objectives, and Measurable Targets
 - Timeline and Coordinator
- Clarify Expected Outcomes: By the end of this session, participants should have a draft action plan outlining key actions/tasks, responsibilities, resource needs, timelines, and risks.
- With bigger groups/ limited time, it is recommended to only discuss selected aspects of the action plan, e.g.,
 - only define actions and risks in one session, and responsibilities and timelines afterwards
 - suggest actions before the session and discuss and further refine them in the session

2. Brainstorming Actions (20 – 30 min)

- Brainstorm the actions/tasks/steps that ought to be included in the action plan with participants? (What needs to be done to reach the objective? Step-by-step)
- Cluster actions into the action plan template.

3. Detail Actions in smaller groups (30 – 45 min)

- Split participants into groups of 4 – 6 people and assign each group with different actions.
- Ask groups to further define each action within the action plan template
 - Who wants to / should be responsible for implementing the action?
 - Who wants to / should support implementing the action?
 - Which personnel, financial, material, and knowledge resources are needed?
 - When can the implementation start? When should it end?
 - What might hinder it? How can these risks be reduced?
- Recording Responses: Groups write into the action plan template.

4. Collate Answers (15 min)

- Facilitators collate the work of the different groups into one large action plan template
- Participants enjoy a break

5. Presenting and Refining Commitments (30 – 45 min)

- Group presentations: Each group shares their actions and how they detailed them.
- Feedback & Alignment: Facilitators and participants discuss overlaps, dependencies, and feasibility. Adjustments are made where needed.

- Refinement of responsibilities: Facilitators and participants discuss responsible and supporting roles and jointly fix them.

6. Finalising Commitments & Next Steps (10 – 30 min)

- Facilitators summarise discussed commitments
- Pledge Wall Activity: Participants write their specific commitment and sign their name to create a sense of accountability.
- Closing Remarks: Facilitators outline follow-up steps, and reinforce the collaborative effort required to achieve success.

Action Plan Template

Focus Area	Briefly describe the specific aspect of the project this action plan addresses (e.g., field testing, stakeholder engagement, policy integration, resource mobilization).
Objectives	Define the objectives of the action plan (e.g., increasing the consumer acceptance of upcycled food products.)
Measurable Targets	Define measurable targets to quantify these objectives (e.g., 20% turnover increase of upcycled food products in intervention markets)
Timeline	Specify the overall timeline of the action plan
Coordinator	Specify the organizations responsible for coordinating that the action plan is executed
Involved	Specify the organizations involved in executing the action plan

List the main steps needed to implement the solution, along with who is responsible for each:

No.	Action	Responsible	Supporting	Resources Needed	Timeline	Risks and Mitigation
	<i>Which steps need to be implemented to reach the objective?</i>	<i>Who is responsible for implementing this?</i>	<i>Who supports the implementation?</i>	<i>Which personnel, financial, material, and knowledge resources are needed?</i>	<i>When can the implementation start? When should it end?</i>	<i>What might hinder it? How can these risks be reduced?</i>
1						
2						
3						
4						

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Consent Form Template

Confidentiality, Data Protection, and Data Usage

We collect three types of data as part of this co-creation session:

1) Personal data (used only for administrative purposes)

- We collect your name, organisation, and email address **to keep a record of who participated** and to communicate with you about the co-creation activities.
- Personal data may be shared only with the PRECIOUS project partners, who require this information for administrative and reporting purposes (e.g., for compliance with EU funder requirements).
- Personal data is **stored securely and separately** from the session results. It will **not** be linked to the anonymised data used for our research and innovation activities.
- Your personal data will be kept confidential and will be deleted **no later than 31 January 2034** after the project has been completed and evaluated by the EU. This ensures we comply with the project's reporting requirements and the GDPR.

2) Demographic data (anonymised, used only for statistical purposes)

- We collect **demographic data (such as gender, age group, and other details) anonymously through a confidential survey** during the session. This data is collected solely for statistical purposes and will not be linked to any personal data or used to identify participants.
- Anonymised demographic data, that cannot be linked to your personal identity, may be shared with PRECIOUS project partners for statistical, research, innovation, reporting, and dissemination purposes.
- We apply the principle of data minimisation, meaning that we only collect the minimum amount of information necessary to achieve the objectives of the project. Your responses are anonymised and will not be used for any other purpose.

3) Data capturing co-creation session results (anonymised, used for research and innovation purposes)

- During the session, we will take notes and document the discussions digitally.
- These records will be **fully anonymised**, meaning they will not include any information that could identify you. The original records will be deleted within 3 months after the session.
- Anonymised data, that cannot be linked to your personal identity, may be shared with all PRECIOUS project partners for research, innovation, reporting, and dissemination purposes.
- The anonymised data may be used in project reports, scientific publications, presentations, and other project-related outputs. It may also be stored in public databases after the project ends to support future research. It will be retained indefinitely.

This study complies with the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679** and the **European Commission's Ethics Guidelines for Research**, particularly:

- **GDPR Article 6 – Lawfulness of Processing:**

Your participation is voluntary, and by agreeing to take part, you consent to the collection and processing of anonymised data. We are also required to keep attendance records for reporting obligations to our funders, which are stored securely and not linked to the anonymised data. The research is conducted in the public interest, aiming to contribute to FLWPR actions.

- **GDPR Article 7 – Conditions for Consent:**

Your consent to participate is freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous. You are free to withdraw your consent at any time without the need to provide justification for your decision and without any negative consequences.

We may use **AI tools for transcription and data processing** of anonymised data. If AI tools are used for transcribing or processing data (such as speech-to-text services or automated analysis), we ensure that the data will be processed in **compliance with the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (2021/0106), as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**.

We ensure that:

- **Only anonymised data is used in AI tools.**
- AI transcription tools do not store or link personal data.
- The use of AI tools for transcription will adhere to transparency and fairness principles, in line with applicable EU regulations.

Rights of Participants

- Your participation in the session is voluntary. You have the right not to answer any question, and to stop your participation at any time and for any reason.
- You have the right to access, correct, or delete your data at any time. To request the access, correction, or deletion of your personal data, please contact the “contact person” specified below.
- You can withdraw your consent to use the data without any negative consequences. Any personal data collected up until the point of withdrawal will be deleted, unless there is a legal obligation to retain it.
- You have the right to lodge a complaint with a data supervisory authority. A full list of the country specific data supervisory authorities can be found [here](#).

Contact information

For any questions or concerns, please contact

Contact person: [please specify contact person for the co-creation session here and provide their email address]

Data Protection Officer & Project Coordinator PRECIOUS:

Deitze Otaduy del Paso, deitze.otaduy@deusto.es

Participant Consent

Please carefully read and sign this consent form. It allows us to use the information that you share with us during the co-creation session research and innovation purposes.

- I voluntarily agree to participate in this co-creation session, which is part of the PRECIOUS project. I am 18 years or older and competent to provide consent.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the project and the co-creation session explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the session.
- I understand that in any publication on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous.
- I have read and understood the "Confidentiality and Data Protection" section of this form, and I agree to the use of my data as outlined there. I had the opportunity to ask questions about the section.
- I agree to being **audio-recorded/ AI-transcribed** during the co-creation session. (**@CoP Leaders:** Please specify what applies to your session)
- I agree that photos and videos are taken during the session and that these can be used for PRECIOUS publications and communication activities. (Please cross out if you do not agree with photos and/or videos).

I have received a copy of this agreement. This consent form is made pursuant to the relevant national, European data protection laws and regulations and personal data treatment obligations.

Date & Location

Name

Signature

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ANNEX 3 – MONITORING DESCRIPTION & TOOLS

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Monitoring & Evaluation Description

The CoP creation and implementation during PRECIOUS WP 6 aims to support that the project outputs and outcomes are relevant to the situation of diverse stakeholders and that they will eventually be disseminated and taken up in practice. Monitoring and evaluation will be conducted in order to assess whether the project is on track to achieve this overarching goal by

- serving as feedback to CoP hosts tailor the individual CoP meetings to the needs and wants of the stakeholders and project tasks; → [Monitoring & Evaluation Description](#) (Annex 3)
- enabling CSCP as WP6 lead as well as the CoP hosts to keep track of essential KPIs and objectives; and
- informing – as essential elements – the *Impact Workshop* (M19), and D6.3, the *Impact assessment and updated stakeholder engagement plan* (M48).
- Using the Meeting report to capture immediately which aspects of the session worked and which did not → [Monitoring & Evaluation Description](#) (Annex 3).

Monitoring checklist

This is a guiding list indicating all the materials and resources the CoP Host is expected to share with the CSCP as WP6 host after the conclusion of each of the 5 CoP meetings conducted to inform and complete the monitoring and evaluation process.

Material	Provided	Not provided
Agenda of the session		
Meeting presentation (if there was one)		
Meeting report (see → Meeting Report Template)		
List of Participants (See → List of Participant Template)		
Consent forms (See → Consent Form Template)		
Participant Survey (See → Participant Survey Template)		
Feedback survey (See → Feedback Survey Template)		

Evaluation Process

The evaluation of PRECIOUS is designed to validate the project's success by tracking the performance of the CoP activities across two key domains: **Process & Participation** and **Impact**. Progress in these two domains will be assessed on a constant basis as well as in a concerted action in the impact workshop (M19), and reported on in D6.3 (M48).

Over the project’s lifetime, CSCP and other project partners will assess whether CoP meetings were implemented as planned, whether all food supply chain stages were sufficiently involved, and whether gender balance targets were met. The CSCP, in collaboration with the CoP hosts and task leads, will also evaluate the extent to which relevant project tasks were meaningfully integrated into CoP sessions. On the impact side, the framework examines whether CoP meetings enhanced stakeholders’ knowledge of FLW reduction strategies, fostered local ownership, initiatives, or led to collaborations that could drive action beyond the project’s

duration. Finally, it considers whether stakeholder feedback influenced the development and validation of other project outputs.

The following Key Performance Indicators will here be considered as being closely connected to the CoPs:

- Specific Outcome 1 (SO1): To create a robust and standardised database of FLWPR actions to provide reliable quantitative data on the environmental footprint of FLW and on the potential impacts of these actions, KPIs:
 - KPI: At least 90% of the FSC stages covered in every UC.
 - KPI: 100% of the food families covered among UCs and CRNs.
 - KPI: 100% of the FLW monitored.
 - KPI: 100% of the stakeholders of the FSC covered among UCs and CRNs.
- Specific Outcome (SO7): To design Communities of Practices that engage relevant local stakeholders to co-create on PRECIOUS FLWPR actions and its assessment
 - KPI: 10 best practices workshops (2/UC+3/CRN+ 5/FLW related projects/platforms and start-ups engagement).
 - KPI: 5 workshops per UC, 4 online workshops per CRNs, 3 EU FLW event participations, and further co-creation and mutual learning activities.
- Specific Outcome 8 (SO8): Promote the adoption of sustainable FLWPR practices and make a real impact in reducing FLW and associated GHG emissions
 - KPI: 20 stakeholders are adopting sustainable FLW practices, and by the end of the Project, this number increases 30%.

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Meeting Report Template

Summary of each CoP Meeting

In order to learn from the meeting and keep track of our Key Performance Indicators and to report back to the European Commission, each CoP Host is requested to summarise each CoP meeting (or CoP activity) in a structured format. For, this purpose, please find a structured reports template below. Please refer to the notes and transcriptions of each session as well as participant feedback while filling in the report.

Session Overview

Purpose	What was the main objective or focus of the session?
Topics	Which topics were discussed during the meeting? List at least 5 topics and/or provide CSCP with the agenda of the session.
Input	Which PRECIOUS tasks have been discussed and tackled and how?
Location	When and where did the session take place? Was it in person, online, or hybrid?
Facilitation/Minutes	Who facilitated the session? Who documented the session?
Participants	Total count of participants Count of participants per food supply chain stage and stakeholder type Gender distribution of participants Were there any notable absences or underrepresented groups? How was the diversity of the participants (e.g., in terms of expertise, sectors, or demographics)?
Materials	Were any materials or resources shared with participants before or during the session?
Documentation	What kind of documentation was produced (e.g., minutes, visual maps, recordings)?
Communication	What is shared with participants as a follow-up? What is shared with project partners as a follow-up?
Consent form	In which form was the consent form provided, discussed, and signed (physically, digitally)?

Facilitation and Stakeholder Dynamics

Interactions	<p>Were people really engaged? Were they participating? Did you sense some apathy in the participants? Here we want to know how they were feeling during the meeting.</p> <p>Rate the mood considering -5 being not engaged to 5 being engaged.</p>
Facilitation methods	<p>What methods, tools, or approaches were used to facilitate the session (e.g., brainstorming, role-playing, world café)?</p> <p>Were these methods effective in achieving the session’s goals? Why or why not?</p>
Insights for future stakeholder engagement	<p>How can important stakeholder groups who were absent from this session be further engaged in future engagement activities?</p> <p>How can lowly engaged participants be better addressed in future engagement activities?</p> <p>How can high engagement of stakeholders be leveraged to strengthen future engagement activities?</p>
Conflicts	<p>Did any conflicts, tensions, or misunderstandings arise? If so, how were they addressed?</p>

Outcomes and Insights

Outcomes	<p>What was achieved during this session? List at least 5 outcomes of the meeting (e.g., ideas, insights, agreements, action points)?</p> <p>Were there any unexpected findings or challenges that emerged?</p> <p>How do the results contribute to the objectives of the Community of Practice as a whole?</p> <p>How do the results support PRECIOUS tasks’ needs for stakeholder input?</p>
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Please provide a brief overview of the action points stemming from the meeting and please indicate, if possible, the deadline and responsible organisation and person for each item. Please add new rows as necessary.

Action point(s)	Followed up by	Until

Reflections and Learnings

Please provide a brief description of the key learnings related to the planning and implementation of the co-creation session: What went well, what needs to be improved for the upcoming meetings etc. Also please reflect on the support that was provided to you and to what extent it was useful to you. Please add new rows as necessary. If you have collected such organisational feedback from participants, please feel free to highlight it in this section.

What went well and will be implemented again in the next session? Think about the place where the session was facilitated, the format, people’s participation, etc.

What needs to be improved? What needs to be modified for next session? Think about the place where the session was facilitated, the format, the homology in people’s participation, etc.

How can the CoP address the stakeholders’ needs and wants in an effort to create FLWPR impact in the region?

How can other project tasks adapt, to mitigate the risk of a lack of uptake of project results by end-users?

What further support would you need?

Did the methods used during this session (e.g., World café), gave a positive outcome? Should they be kept for next sessions? If not, why?

Other

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Participant Survey Template

Funded by
the European Union

Participant Survey

This anonymous survey is designed to gather demographic information on participants in accordance with GDPR requirements. The data collected will remain confidential and will not be linked to any personal identities. It solely serves the purpose to inform the meeting report.

Question 1: Which stakeholder group do you belong to? (please diversify the groups)

- Primary Production
(e.g., agricultural goods)
- Processing and Manufacturing
- Retail & Wholesale
- Redistribution
(e.g., food banks, apps, food sharing)
- Restaurants and food services
- Consumers, Households, and Representatives
(e.g., local citizen, community organisers, consumer-centred NGOs)
- Academics and Researchers
(e.g., university faculty, researchers, food scientists)
- Policy Makers and Public Sector Bodies
(e.g., government officials, local authorities, policy advisors, environmental agencies)
- Other non-food stakeholders
(e.g., disposal, waste, composting, energy, technology, other ...)

Question 2: Which age group do you belong to?

- 18-34 years
- 35 - 54 years
- 55 - 69 years
- 70+ years

Question 3: Which gender do you consider yourself?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / Third gender
- Prefer not to say

@CoP leaders: Please feel free to add any additional demographic questions you believe are relevant for your Community of Practice. However, please ensure the questions remain broad and non-specific to protect the anonymity of participants.

Feedback Survey

@CoP Leaders: Please adapt the listed questions to the setting and framework of your individual CoP meeting and feel free to add any other questions that you find relevant.

- **Make sure to mainly use the rating questions and only include 2 or 3 open answer questions.** Please format the open answer questions, so that participants have sufficient space to answer.
- This questionnaire can either be made available to participants in paper or transferred to an online format (i.e., survey monkey, Google forms).

General information

Have you attended previous meetings in the Community of Practice?

- Yes
- No

How useful did you find the CoP meeting overall for your food waste reduction and prevention ambitions?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Did you have the opportunity to actively participate/share your opinions during the meeting?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Did the facilitation methods provide good opportunities for collaboration and exchange of information with other stakeholders?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Did you feel comfortable participating in this CoP meeting?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

Do you have any suggestions for improving the CoP meeting?

Do you have any wish or topic suggestion for the next CoP meeting?

What did you like most about the CoP meeting?

Do you have any other feedback you would like to give?
